

*Establishing a Framework for Quantifiable Evidence and Impact of
Ecosystem Change Throughout the Lifecycle of UK Floating Offshore Wind
Farms (EQUIFy)*

WP1 – Co-Development & Co-Delivery

D1.2 – Equify Data Architecture

Author: Thomas Mansfield (tma@pml.ac.uk)

Version: 1.0

Date: 1st October 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17178362

EQUIfy is part of the ECOFlow program, funded by UKRI (NE/Z504099/1) and The Crown Estate.

Executive Summary

This document is the first issue or a living document that sets out the initial design and vision for the EQUiFY Data Architecture, a key deliverable within the ECOFlow program. Its primary aim is to provide a central, authoritative resource for identifying all datasets generated throughout the project, ensuring that each dataset is clearly documented with licensing and sharing guidance. By doing so, the document supports all project partners in understanding and making full use of the data sharing infrastructure available to them.

The architecture is built on a federated model, allowing data creators to retain full control over their datasets by hosting them on their own infrastructure. Rather than centralizing data storage, the system enables partners to register their datasets with the project, making them discoverable and accessible through a central ERDDAP data portal managed by Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML). This approach ensures that data ownership, access policies, and updates remain with the data providers, while still enabling seamless discovery, access, and integration for all project partners. ERDDAP acts as the central access point, offering both user-friendly tools and robust APIs for programmatic access. It allows users to search, subset, and combine datasets, and to download data in a variety of formats, with licensing and citation guidance provided for each dataset. Where necessary, authentication can be configured to control access to sensitive data. The architecture also aligns metadata with external standards, such as those from the NERC Vocabulary Services, supporting interoperability and advancing the FAIR data principles.

Importantly, this document is intended to serve as a practical guide for all project partners, helping them to understand, access, and utilize the data sharing infrastructure. There is also a potential opportunity to expand this federated architecture to support the wider ECOFlow program, should that be required in the future.

Finally, the project is committed to continuous improvement. Lessons learned throughout the implementation and operation of the data architecture will be collected and incorporated into future updates, ensuring that the system evolves to meet the needs of all stakeholders and maximizes the impact of the project's data resources.

This living document will be updated throughout the EQUiFY project to capture the evolving needs of the EQUiFY data community. A final issue is expected to be issued in late 2028.

Contents

Executive Summary	2
Contents	3
1 Introduction	4
1.1 Scope	4
1.2 EQUiFy Data Management and Sharing Considerations	4
1.2.1 Data Management, Use and Sharing	4
1.2.2 EQUiFy Project Data Sharing License	4
1.2.3 Expected EQUiFY Data	4
1.2.4 Data Retention and Disposal.....	10
2 EcoFlow Data Architecture Design	11
2.1 High level needs for the EQUiFy data architecture.....	11
2.2 Objectives.....	11
2.3 Architecture Design; A federated approach	12
2.3.1 Architecture Design – In-situ data federate	12
2.3.2 Architecture Design – Remote sensing and model data federate.....	14
2.3.3 Architecture Design – Socio-economic data federate	14
2.4 Opportunities for expansion beyond the current project scope	15
3 Implementation of the data architecture - A worked example	16
4 Future plans and next steps	18
5 References.....	19
Annex A: EQUiFY data architecture; Opportunities for a multi-institute data staging area	20

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document forms the first of two planned deliveries of the EQUIFY Data Architecture. The document describes the planned EQUIFY data architecture, providing a guidebook to project members and external stakeholders on managing data related to the project throughout their lifecycle. Particular emphasis is placed on describing the responsibilities, processes and tools available to the EQUIFY team to support the creation of rich metadata and enable the controlled sharing of emerging datasets with project partners and external stakeholders.

This document is intended to compliment and support the EQUIFY Data Management and Sharing Plan, a document that is managed by the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) in close collaboration with the EQUIFY team, to summarise staff responsibilities, data collection policies, data quality and arrangements for long-term management of data beyond the project. The EQUIFY data architecture plan aligns with PML's Scientific Data Management Policy [1] and UKRI's Natural Environment Research Council's data sharing policy [2].

An updated version of this document will be issued once the majority of the EQUIFY data collection activities have been completed (M44), providing an implementation record for the data architecture described in this document, along with a series of lessons learned.

1.2 EQUIFY Data Management and Sharing Considerations

Data management and sharing considerations are structured across the data lifecycle.

1.2.1 Data Management, Use and Sharing

Initially, PML's ERDDAP [3] service will enable project partners and external users to access locally stored data in near real time with additional data brokers provided where required. Subsequently, quality checked and processed data sets will be archived at the relevant data centres, providing a persistent findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) [4] data resource.

1.2.2 EQUIFY Project Data Sharing License

To support the timely sharing of data within the EQUIFY project, the following project licence text has been developed, providing two project specific licences that can be utilised by data owners

[Option 1] *Permission is granted to EQUIFY project partner institutes and interested parties to use this dataset for research and analytical purposes only. Redistribution, republication, or any form of data sharing with unauthorized third parties is strictly prohibited without prior written consent from the data owner. All users must acknowledge the source of the dataset in any publications or outputs.*

[Option 2] *Permission is granted to EQUIFY project partner institutes to use this dataset for research and analytical purposes only. Redistribution, republication, or any form of data sharing with unauthorized third parties is strictly prohibited without prior written consent from the data owner. All users must acknowledge the source of the dataset in any publications or outputs.*

1.2.3 Expected EQUIFY Data

Table 1 contains an overview of the data expected to be created or modified by the EQUIFY project, with key attributes listed that will allow the data to be correctly managed, distributed and projected throughout the subsequent stages of the project life cycle.

Table 1 - Expected EQUiFy Datasets

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
FLOW engineering model data for momentum and TKE parameterisations	T. Nishino	≈ 10 GB	TBC (non-proprietary formats preferred)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • After 6 months of data generation: OGL [5] 	University of Oxford	Oxford University Research Archive (ORA)	Yes
Celtic Sea ocean and ecosystem model (FVCOM-ERSEM) outputs	J. Clark	≈ 150 GB (volume may increase depending on the number and length of scenarios)	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • After 6 months of data generation: OGL [5] 	Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML)	CEDA (Archival managed by BODC)	Yes
Plankton Imaging (IFCB and Pi-10 data)	J. Clark	≈ 200 GB	.csv and .png	OGL [5]	PML	BODC (TBC)	Yes
USV NRT ecosystem monitoring data – CTD, Chla, met-underway	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • After 6 months of data generation: OGL 	PML	BODC	Yes
USV delayed mode ecosystem monitoring data – CTD, Chl-a, met-underway	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) 	PML	BODC	Yes

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After 6 months of data generation: OGL [5] 			
USV ecosystem monitoring data – Fishery Acoustics	B. Williamson	<p>≈ 100's GB (Raw data)</p> <p>≈ 100 MB (data products)</p>	TBC (<i>non-proprietary formats preferred</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) 2 years after project completion: OGL 	University of the Highlands and Islands (UHI)	<i>None for raw data. (Note: There is a lack of standardisation and these are large datasets). Data products will be archived alongside publications.</i>	<p>No</p> <p>(Except for data products that support publication)</p>
NRT glider data: T,S, DO, Chl, CDOM, BBP	MARS	≈ MB	.nc .tbd, .sbd, .cac	OGL	PML	BODC	No
Recovery Glider Data – (i.e. the data from the glider SD card when the glider is recovered)	MARS	≈ MB & GB for turbulence data	.ebd, .dbd., cac.. PDO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) 2 years after project completion: OGL 	PML	BODC	No
Delayed Mode Glider Data: TS, DO, Chl, DOM, BPP, TKE dissipation	J. Wihsgott	≈ 5 GB	.nc & non-proprietary format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) 	PML	BODC	Yes

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 years after project completion: OGL 			
WCO L4 datasets (Inc. CTD, ocean currents, meteorological data and weekly biogeochemical sampling)	T. Mansfield	MBs	.csv	OGL [5]	PML	BODC	Yes (DOI assigned to annual additions)
eDNA Data	J. Robidart	MBs	.csv	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • After 6 months of data generation: OGL [5] 	National Oceanography Centre (NOC)	National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) (TBC)	Yes, is data archived within OBIS
Regional Environmental Prediction (REP) model outputs	S. Berthou	≈ 100 TB total (Approx 250 GB used by the project)	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within 6 months of data generation: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • After 6 months of data generation: OGL [5] 	MetOffice	MetOffice DAC	No
Moored instrument data – Fishery Echosounder	B. Williamson	≈ 1 TB	TBC (non-proprietary formats preferred)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) 	UHI	None for raw data. (Note: There is a lack of standardisation)	No (Except for data products that support publication)

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 years after project completion: OGL 		<i>and these are large datasets. Data products will be archived alongside publications.</i>	
Moored instrument data – Current velocities (Raw)	J. Wihsgott and B. Williamson	≈ 2 GB or more	TBC (<i>non-proprietary formats preferred</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Licence [Option 2] • At project completion: Licence [Option 2] • 2 years after project completion: OGL 	Marine Directorate (MD) / UHI	BODC (<i>submitted with processed data</i>)	No
Moored instrument data – Current velocities (Processed)	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • 2 years after project completion: OGL 	PML	BODC	Yes
Moored instrument data – CTD	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) 	MD / UHI	BODC	Yes

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 years after project completion: OGL 			
Moored instrument data – Chl-A	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • 2 years after project completion: OGL 	MD / UHI	BODC	Yes
Moored instrument data – Oxygen	J. Wihsgott	≈ 500 MB	.nc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 1]) • 2 years after project completion: OGL 	MD / UHI	BODC	Yes
Moored instrument data – Cetacean click detector	B. Williamson	≈ 1 TB	TBC (<i>non-proprietary formats preferred</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the project: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) • At project completion: Project licence (1.2.2 [Option 2]) • 2 years after project completion: OGL 	UHI	<i>None (No known data archiving centre for passive acoustic data). Data products will be made available alongside publications where required.</i>	No

Dataset Description	Dataset Contact Name(s)	Estimated Data Volume	Data Format	Licence	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Contact	Data Archiving Centre	DOI Required
Database of evidence for the impact of Offshore Wind Farms on Marine Ecosystem Services (ORIES)	S. Watson	5 MB	.csv	OGL	PML	<i>CEDA, managed by the UKERC Energy Data Centre</i>	Yes, update to https://doi.org/10.5286/ukerc.edc.000961
Inputs / outputs of the Dynamic Bayesian Network Ecosystem Models (DBN)	N. Trifonova	MBs	.csv	OGL	University of Aberdeen	<i>CEDA, with data products will be made available alongside publications where required.</i>	No
ASPACE raw data	Ana Queiros and Liz Talbot	≈10 TB	.txt, NetCDF, .jpeg	Proprietary	PML	None	No
ASPACE analysis	Ana Queiros and Liz Talbot	≈1 GB	Shapefiles	OGL	PML	DASSH	Yes
ASPACE MAS values matrix	Ana Queiros and Liz Talbot	500 KB	NetCDF	OGL	PML	DASSH	Yes
	Total data volume	≈12.75 TB <i>(<1 TB deposited with DAC)</i>					

1.2.4 Data Retention and Disposal

PML will periodically review all data maintained within the EQUIFy data storage infrastructure, establishing whether it should be maintained, transferred or disposed of. Data registered at the data archive centres are expected to provide a long-term, persistent resource.

2 EcoFlow Data Architecture Design

2.1 High level needs for the EQUIFy data architecture

The Ecological Effects of Floating Offshore Wind (EcoFlow) program comprises of three projects, EQUIFy, FrontLines and eSWEETS³. Keynote talks at the EcoFlow kick-off meeting (14th Nov 2024) set out the objectives and aims of the program, with key snapshots including:

“The expectation is for scientists to engage early as information emerges and not wait for publication; incomplete, uncertain knowledge is OK.”

*“This is different to normal science –
We’re aiming to provide information early.”*

The resulting EQUIFy data architecture design aims to identify opportunities and develop a data management architecture that will form the central foundation to the program’s ability to deliver timely, impactful and cross-project science outputs.

This architecture will be developed following iterative and incremental development principles, aligned with data management best practice [6]. Specifically, a number of *epic user stories* will be identified that set out the objectives of the development. These epics, along with lower level user stories will be presented and reviewed at scheduled meetings throughout the project, allowing stakeholders to feedback, iterate and incrementally develop data architecture capabilities through co-design processes.

2.2 Objectives

The high-level needs and objectives of an in-project findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) data staging area are captured in three Epic User Stories:

Epic User Story 1 – Efficiency

As an EQUIFy scientist, I want my data to be FAIR early in the project so that I can reuse automated visualisation, quality checking and processing tools.

Epic User Story 2 - Control

As an EQUIFy project manager, I want to clearly communicate the dissemination and quality limitations of project data so that I can ensure quality and compliance.

Epic User Story 3 - Impact

As an EQUIFy funder, I want scientists to access the data that they need to that their outputs optimise data-driven decision making processes.

2.3 Architecture Design; A federated approach

EQUIFy brings together expertise from across engineering, environmental and social sciences to build on the best emerging knowledge of how current wind farms are effecting our seas. To achieve these scientific objectives, the project's data architecture is required to support the sharing of data among a range of multi-disciplinary and multi-sector project entities. As detailed in Table 1, this diversity is reflected in the range of datasets that need to be shared and managed. A federated approach to data architecture design in the EQUIFy project is essential to harmonize the contributions of diverse data communities, spanning in-situ observations, remote sensing, and socio-economic domains, while preserving their autonomy over standards, governance, and contextual relevance. This federated approach builds upon lessons from the SyncED-Ocean project [7] and aligns federates to distinct scientific communities to enable scalable interoperability and foster trust across disciplines. Crucially, this architecture supports the seamless integration of varied data types into decision support tools through a limited set of well-defined API interfaces, ensuring consistent access, efficient data exchange, and actionable insights. This structure empowers EQUIFy to deliver equitable, transparent, and context-aware data services that reflect the complexity of environmental and societal systems. An overview of the federated approach that supports these aims is shown in Figure 1, with a federate provided for metadata rich in-situ data, large remote sensing and model data as well as diverse socio-economic and socio-ecological data all available via a subset of aligned machine readable data APIs.

Figure 1 - A federated approach to data provision

2.3.1 Architecture Design – In-situ data federate

EQUIFy, proposes to build upon successes of recent projects (e.g. SyncED-Ocean) to develop a federated data architecture that enables scientists to create machine-readable FAIR data as data is created by a range of sources throughout the project. This approach brings a wide number of benefits at minimal cost, focusing on timely discovery, exchange and combination of data among distributed project partners that enhances the quality of the scientific outputs.

This project implements a federated data architecture that enables scientists and data creators to host their datasets on their own institutional infrastructure, while still making those datasets discoverable and accessible through a centralized portal managed by PML. In this model, with an overview provided in Figure 2, data ownership and control remain entirely with the providers, who supply links to their hosted datasets. These links are then integrated into PML's configuration of ERDDAP, a versatile data server that facilitates both human-friendly and programmatic access to scientific data.

Figure 2 - Overview of the proposed in-situ FAIR data staging area.

ERDDAP serves as the central interface for users to explore, access, and interact with the federated datasets. It supports a wide range of data access methods, including RESTful and OPeNDAP APIs, and provides tools that allow users to subset or combine datasets according to their specific research needs. Data can be downloaded in multiple formats, such as CSV and NetCDF, with ERDDAP handling the necessary conversions automatically. Each dataset is accompanied by appropriate licensing information and citation guidance, ensuring that data usage complies with the limitations described within Table 1 of this document. Where required, authentication mechanisms can be configured within ERDDAP to control access to sensitive or restricted datasets to specific users.

The metadata associated with each dataset will be aligned with external standards, such as those provided by the NERC Vocabulary Services [8], with the aim of providing compliance to the MEDIN metadata guidance [9]. This alignment enhances semantic interoperability and contributes significantly to the maturity of the FAIR data principles, making data more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The architecture also supports streamlined data archiving as ERDDAP can be linked to tools provided by the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS) centres to enable the automated archival of datasets at the conclusion of the project. This approach reduces the overheads required with ensuring the long-term preservation and continued accessibility of valuable scientific data after the EQUIFY project concludes.

Crucially, this federated approach ensures that data providers retain full control over their data at all times. Hosting remains local, and any updates, access restrictions, or metadata enhancements can be managed directly by the data owners. This model fosters trust, flexibility, and collaboration, while providing a robust and scalable framework for scientific data sharing and reuse.

2.3.2 Architecture Design – Remote sensing and model data federate

The PIER (Platform for Integrated Environmental Research) [10] [11] portal, developed by PML, provides a robust, web-based environment for sharing and visualising Earth observation (EO) and model data. Designed for accessibility and ease of use, it supports a wide range of geospatial research outputs from satellite-derived products to in situ measurements and model simulations without requiring users to install software. Hosted on PML’s high-performance infrastructure, PIER enables interactive access to terabytes of data through a browser, making it a valuable tool for both research and commercial applications. Its modular design and ongoing development ensure it remains adaptable to project-specific needs, supporting open, visual, and user-friendly data dissemination.

2.3.3 Architecture Design – Socio-economic data federate

The socio-economic and socio-ecological data federate within the EQUIFY architecture is designed to support the discovery, access, and integration of diverse non-geospatial datasets through a CKAN-based data service. Leveraging the CKAN API, this federate enables programmatic access to structured metadata and datasets, facilitating interoperability with other components of the architecture and integration into decision support tools. Metadata is curated using the MEDIN non-geospatial metadata standard, ensuring consistency and discoverability across environmental and social science domains. Additionally, the federate incorporates best practices from the UK Data Service, promoting responsible data management, documentation, and reuse. This approach ensures that complex socio-environmental datasets are both accessible and usable for interdisciplinary research and policy applications. An overview of this architecture is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Overview of the proposed socio-economic FAIR data staging area.

2.4 Opportunities for expansion beyond the current project scope

The federated data architecture established in this project is inherently scalable and well-suited for integration with other initiatives within the ECOFLOW program.

As additional projects generate new datasets, these can be incorporated into the existing ERDDAP infrastructure by simply linking to the data hosted on each contributor's infrastructure. This approach, shown in Figure 4, would maintain the principle of data ownership and control, while enabling seamless access and interoperability across the program.

Figure 4 - Overview of a potential, expanded EcoFlow FAIR data staging area.

To further enhance human-centric data discovery, ERDDAP could be extended with Marine Data Exchange (MDE) toolsets which, due to the co-alignment with MEDIN metadata guidance, would provide intuitive interfaces and advanced search capabilities tailored to the needs of marine scientists and stakeholders.

These enhancements will allow users to more easily locate and understand datasets, regardless of their origin within the ECOFLOW program. As new datasets become available, they can be immediately exposed through ERDDAP, making them accessible to the entire ECOFLOW community. The architecture supports careful control over data dissemination, with configurable access permissions and licensing options that ensure data is shared responsibly and in accordance with contributor preferences.

This expanded integration not only strengthens collaboration across ECOFLOW projects but also reinforces the FAIR data principles by promoting consistent metadata standards, discoverability, and reuse. The ability to federate and harmonize data from multiple sources within a single, user-friendly portal represents a significant step forward in the program's data management maturity.

3 Implementation of the data architecture - A worked example

At the time of writing this report, the first EQUIFY data collection activity has recently drawn to a close. The collection of initial datasets provides an opportunity to provide a worked example of the planned dataset, providing a tangible example of how data management throughout the EQUIFY project will be managed.

The data collection that will be described in detail is the deployment of an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) sensor deployed from 14th August 2025. Upon recovery of the sensor, the raw data file was transferred onto servers within PML and processed to provide a useable dataset. These data have been linked to an ERDDAP, with metadata developed in collaboration with the responsible scientist and the EQUIFY data architect. These data, with accompanying metadata, are now available to be shared throughout the EQUIFY consortium.

An overview of this initial data pipeline is shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6 which provide an abstracted view of the data pipeline that can be compared to the data architecture designs and a set of screenshots that depict the specific implementation respectively.

Figure 5 - An abstracted view of the ADCP data pipeline

```

NC_GLOBAL (
  String cdm_data_type "Other";
  String history
  "2025-08-27T11:06:35Z (local files)
  2025-08-27T11:06:35Z
  https://erddap.eoform.space/erddap/tabledap/equify_adcp_level10.html";
  String infoUrl "https://pml.ac.uk/news/what-are-the-potential-effects-
of-floating-offshore-wind-on-marine-ecosystems/";
  String institution "Plymouth Marine Laboratory";
  String keywords "adcp, data, ecoflow, equify, file, identifier,
lastModified, modified, name, ocean, pml, size, synced, time";
  String license
  "The data may be used and redistributed for free but is not intended
  
```

Machine readable, FAIR data available to support the project

PML Plymouth Marine Laboratory PML's ERDDAP Easy access to scientific data at PML

ERDDAP > List of All Datasets

11 matching datasets, listed in alphabetical order

Grid Data	Sub-DAP	Table Data	Table Data	Table Data	Table Data	Title	Summary	FGDC Metadata	Background Info	RSS	Email	Institution	Dataset ID
set	data	graph	files	files	files	* The List of All Active Datasets in this ERDDAP *		M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	allDatasets
set	data	graph	files	files	files	AUT - Inherent Optical Property (IOP) core pigment discrete data		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	AUT_2020_8074_7337
data						AUT - Inherent Optical Property (IOP) near-continuous data		M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	AUT_2024_CM6_0089
						EQUIFY - Kiorline ADCP current velocity V2.0		M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	IM_25_eqi_104c_6c56_6a3a
						MONOCLE - Solar Tracking Radiometry Platform (So-Rad) Data		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	public_sorad_public_view_5p_mil_inspire
set	data	graph	files	files	files	SynCED-Ocean - Non-QC'd Glider Data Files from NOC		M	background			NOC	bookData_584_4067_51ae
set	data	graph	files	files	files	SynCED-Ocean - Realtime QC'd OceanGliders Trajectory File		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	qr_outputs_table
						WCO - E1 CTD Data		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	E1_ctd_0a24_0895_0956
						WCO - L4 CTD Data		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	L4_Seq_0554_2679
						WCO - R/V Plymouth Quest Underway Data		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	Underway_1237_711d_c532
set	data	graph	files	files	files	WCOF Validation - Meteorological data from Rame Head		F I M	background			Plymouth Marine L.	rame_51f_c01a_2209

Metadata development and recording underway

ADCP's deployed from RRS Discovery (14th August 2025)

Figure 6 - Screenshots of the data pipeline implementation.

As an example of the services provided to EQUIFY data users, the ADCP data can be viewed at the QR code displayed in , with the discovery metadata available from the QR code provided in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7 - QR code providing example ADCP data from the EQUIFY project

Figure 8 - QR code providing discovery metadata for the example ADCP data.

4 Future plans and next steps

This report represents the first of two planned document releases for the project. It outlines the design and implementation of the federated data architecture, guiding data access, interoperability, and control.

A second version of this document, planned for M44 of the EQUIFy project, will provide a detailed record of how individual datasets were configured within the architecture. This will include documentation that supports scientists in locating, accessing, and using the data most relevant to their research. The configuration records will enhance transparency and will serve as a practical guide for engaging with the federated system.

Finally, a lessons learnt process will be initiated throughout the implementation of this data architecture. This process will capture observations from across the project, identifying both successful strategies and areas where improvements can be made. These insights will be analysed and used to inform future projects, contributing to the ongoing evolution and refinement of the federated data architecture approach.

Together, these two document releases aim to provide a comprehensive view of the architecture and its application, while supporting continuous improvement and knowledge sharing across the scientific data community.

5 References

- [1] Plymouth Marine Laboratory, "PML Scientific Data Management Policy," PML, Plymouth, UK, 2023 (Version 5).
- [2] M. Thorley and S. Callaghan, "NERC Data Policy - Guidance Notes," UNRI Natural Environment Research Council, 2019.
- [3] National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), "ERDDAP > Information," NOAA, [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/erddap/information.html>. [Accessed 22 September 2025].
- [4] Mark D. Wilkinson et al., "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship," *Scientific Data*, vol. 3, no. 18, 2016.
- [5] UK Government, "Open Government Licence (V3)," The National Archives, [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/>. [Accessed 22 September 2025].
- [6] DAMA International, Data Management Body of Knowledge (DAMA BoK), Vancouver, USA.: DAMA International, 2017.
- [7] T. Mansfield; J. Wihsgott; J. Skakala; P. Menon; E. Gardner; S. Kay; and M. Palmer, , "Lessons Learned in Establishing an Environmental Digital Twin," in *IEEE OCEANS*, pp. 1-10, doi: 10.1109/OCEANS58557.2025.11104760, Brest, France., 2025.
- [8] BODC, "NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)," BODC, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/products/web_services/vocab/. [Accessed June 2023].
- [9] MEDIN Standards Working Group, "Guidance notes for the production of discovery metadata for the Marine Environmental Data and Information Network," MEDIN Standards Working Group, Southampton, UK., 2022.
- [10] Plymouth Marine Laboratory, "PML Model data portal," PML, [Online]. Available: <https://portal.ecosystem-modelling.pml.ac.uk/>. [Accessed September 2025].
- [11] NEODAAS, "NEODAAS Data Portal," NEODAAS is hosted at Plymouth Marine Laboratory, overseen by the National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO) and funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://data.neodaas.ac.uk/visualisation/>. [Accessed September 2025].

Annex A: EQUIFY data architecture; Opportunities for a multi-institute data staging area

This annex contains a slide pack that has been presented at various EQUIFY and ECOFLOW program meetings to describe the opportunities and potential benefits of expanding the EQUIFY data architecture across the complete EQUIFY project portfolio.

PML | Plymouth Marine
Laboratory

SCIENCE FOR OCEAN ACTION

X @PlymouthMarine
@PlymouthMarineLab
in Follow us on LinkedIn
www.pml.ac.uk

Equify Data Architecture Opportunities for a multi-institute data staging area

Tom Mansfield | PML
tma@pml.ac.uk
27th August 2025

EcoFlow Program Aims

Key quotes from the EcoFlow kick off meeting (Nov. 2024)

“The expectation is for scientists to engage early as information emerges and not wait for publication; incomplete, uncertain knowledge is OK.”

“This is different to normal science – We’re aiming to provide information early.”

How can the data architecture support these aims?

Equify Staging Area

Data Architecture

Machine readable, FAIR data to support the project

 ERDDAP
Easier access to scientific data

Simplified data archiving

FAIR data available as program progresses

Equify Staging Area

A worked example from the first Equify cruise

Machine readable, FAIR data to support the project

ERDDAP
Easier access to scientific data

Metadata developed and recorded

ADCP Data


```

NC_GLOBAL (
  String odm_data_type "Other";
  String history
  "2025-08-27T11:06:35Z (local files)
  2025-08-27T11:06:35Z
  https://erddap.eoform.space/erddap/tabledap/equify_adcp_level0.html";
  String infoUrl "https://pml.ac.uk/news/what-are-the-potential-effects-
  of-floating-offshore-wind-on-marine-ecosystems/";
  String institution "Plymouth Marine Laboratory";
  String keywords "adcp, data, ecoflow, equify, file, identifier,
  lastModified, modified, name, ocean, pml, size, synced, time";
  String license
  "The data may be used and redistributed for free but is not intended
  
```

Machine readable, FAIR data available to support the project

PML's ERDDAP
Easier access to scientific data of PML

ERDDAP > List of All Datasets

11 matching datasets, listed in alphabetical order:

Grid Data	Sub-DAP	Total Data	Make Data	W	Source	Title	Sum	PODC	Back	ESS	R	Institution	Dataset ID
Lat	Lon	Files	Grp	Files	Files		Min	Min/Max	ground	Site	Mail		
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	"The List of All Active Datasets in the ERDDAP"			background			Plymouth Marine L.	adatasets
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	AMT - Inherent Optical Property (IOP) time segmented discrete data			background			Plymouth Marine L.	AMT_2016_2017_2107
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	AMT - Inherent Optical Property (IOP) near continuous data			background			Plymouth Marine L.	AMT_2014_2016_2018
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	Equity - Near-QCX, non-processed ADCP files			background			Plymouth Marine L.	equity_2014_2016
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	MONOCUL - Bathy Tracking Radiometry Platform (On-board) Data			background			Plymouth Marine L.	monocul_2014_2016
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	SyncED-Coupler - Near-ADCP Glider Data Files from NOAA			Other				2_218
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	SyncED-Coupler - Realtime QCX OceanGliders Trajectory File			Other				2_218
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	WCO - E1 CTX Data			Other				218
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	WCO - LACTO Data			Other				2_218
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	WCO - R.V. Plymouth Glider Underway Data			Other				2_218
lat	lon	graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	WCOXP Validation - Meteorological data from flame heat			background			Plymouth Marine L.	wam_218_218

Metadata development and recording underway

Logbook scans

Unprocessed data files

ADCP's deployed from RRS Discovery (14th August 2025)

Equify Staging Area

Future opportunities

Recap and potential next steps

- The Equify data architecture aims to support the early creation and exchange of FAIR data among project partners, as data validation and verification continues.

This approach closely aligns with the EcoFlow funders aims and could be adopted across the program

- *Note: This would be an expansion of exiting scope*

This approach could be further enhanced with the integration of MDE tools to enhance data discoverability

- *Note: This would be an expansion of exiting scope*

“The expectation is for scientists to engage early as information emerges and not wait for publication; incomplete, uncertain knowledge is OK.”

“This is different to normal science – We’re aiming to provide information early.”